

Reduction of the market splitting occurrences: A Dynamic Line Rating approach for the 2030 Iberian day-ahead market scenarios

Hugo Algarvio, António Couto and Ana Estanqueiro
Renewable Energy and Energy Efficiency Unit,
LNEG—National Laboratory of Energy and Geology,
1649-038 Lisboa, Portugal
{hugo.algarvio,antonio.couto,ana.estanqueiro}@lneg.pt

Rui Carvalho, Gabriel Santos, Ricardo Faia, Pedro Faria and Zita Vale
GECAD - Research Group on Intelligent Engineering and Computing
for Advanced Innovation and Development, LASI - Intelligent
Systems Associate Laboratory, Polytechnic of Porto,
4249-015 Porto, Portugal
{rugco,gjs,rff,pnf,zav}@isep.ipp.pt

Abstract—Typically, Transmission System Operators apply power flow models with Seasonal Line Rating prescriptions to compute the ampacity of power lines, in a process that enables to obtain the cross-border capacity for trading between different countries or market zones. These seasonal-dependent models rely on fixed conservative meteorological conditions throughout the year, underestimating the real-time transmission capacity of overhead lines. This can contribute to market splitting occurrences, i.e., a situation where the cleared power flow between different market zones of the coupled market is superior to the cross-border capacity, separating markets, which brings economic losses to market participants. Dynamic Line Rating analysis allows computing the overhead lines' capacity considering the weather conditions that influence the power line's thermal dynamics. This work presents a study that applies the CIGRÉ 601 model in cross-border power lines between Portugal and Spain to quantify the reduction in market splitting occurrences in the day-ahead Iberian market considering based on the installed capacities from the 2030 national energy and climate plans. Comparing with the seasonal approach, dynamic line rating enabled to reduce the number of market splitting occurrences from 1512 to 514, reducing the electricity costs by more than 1% and the price difference from 19 to 12 €/MWh.

Keywords— Cross-border capacity; Day-ahead market; Dynamic Line Rating, Market splitting, Seasonal Line Rating.

I. INTRODUCTION

Most Transmission System Operators (TSOs) use a “steady-state” thermal equilibrium model using reference conservative weather conditions to design the maximum seasonal ampacity allowed per line, known as the Seasonal Line Rating (SLR) [1]-[3]. They use reference values for the incident wind speed between 0.5 and 0.61 m/s and for the irradiance between 1000 and 1150 W/m². Normally the reference value of the ambient air temperature is adjusted seasonally and the wind direction is neglected. These reference values are different from the ones used by the cables manufacturers in their tests, performed to define the limit ampacities of the cables [4]-[6]. On the other hand, numerical Dynamic Line Rating (DLR)

models such as the IEEE 738-2023 [7], the Kuipers & Brown [8] and the CIGRÉ [9] models can enable to accurately assess the real-time transmission capacity of overhead lines. Several studies indicate that on average DLR allows to increase the energy transmitted over the estimated capacity using SLR between 10% to 30%, and also identify that the line rating is underestimated around 80% of the time [1]-[3],[10]-[12]. Considering forecast models with low errors is critical to a reliable DLR analysis used by TSOs and utilities [13]-[15].

Traditionally, electricity markets are divided into wholesale and retail markets. Wholesale markets are composed of long-term bilateral contracts and two spot markets based on auctions, the day-ahead (DAM) and the intraday markets. Spot markets are cleared using the system marginal pricing theory, which has the goal of increasing the general welfare of the participants [16]. TSOs have to evaluate the feasibility of the deals to avoid grid congestion events and guarantee the security of the power system. Therefore, when planning the power flow of such transactions, TSOs use the SLR approach to identify the maximum ampacity of the lines. This situation can make some of the bids unfeasible, leading to increased market prices and decreased the overall welfare of the participants [17]. In coupled regions, this can also result in market splitting occurrences in the interconnection exchange between regions. They also manage the balancing markets computing the hourly secondary and tertiary reserve requirements and prices considering the seasonal line limits and the real-time unbalance between supply and demand. Those prices are used in the imbalance settlement mechanisms to charge Balancing Responsible Parties for deviations [18].

Considering the 2030 ambitious European Union goals to increase the share of renewable energy sources (RES) in the power system and harmonize prices, as denoted in the Internal Market of Electricity goals, there is a need to reinforce the national and the cross-border transmission capacity of the grid [19],[20]. This reinforcement represents a costly and lengthy process, and it can be partially mitigated by adopting DLR

models. Therefore, using DLR models can be important on the long-run by avoiding the construction of new lines but also on the short-run by avoiding market splitting, grid congestion, RES curtailments and the degradation of the power lines [21],[22].

The OptiRES.Lines tool developed and detailed presented in [21], is a publicly available tool that uses meteorological data and the power lines characteristics to test different DLR methods. For instance, in [12], this tool tested the CIGRÉ 601 model in five different overhead aluminium conductor steel reinforced cables of two regions in Portugal with different weather conditions. It was used a numerical weather prediction (NWP) model to forecast the meteorological conditions for a given spatial resolution [12]. This resolution is used to define the number of sectors in each line. For a specific hour and power line, the DLR is defined by the critical sector, which is the one with worst cooling conditions according to cable characteristics, transported capacity, and atmospheric conditions. It was concluded that half of the transmission lines operated, on average, at a rate of 25% and 42% lower than the DLR for each region. Another study considered the application of DLR in the cross-border transmission lines (also known as tie-lines) connecting Portugal and Spain, and the observed generation and consumption values for both countries as well as the export/import capacities in 2018. Results show that DLR enabled to reduce the number of market-splitting hours of MIBEL in 2018, from 456 to 186 hours [17]. In those hours, the application of DLR increased the price harmonization between market zones by reducing the price difference from an average value of 8.89 €/MWh to 6.12 €/MWh. Against this background, this work aims to verify the impact of the DLR in reducing the occurrences of market splitting in the day-ahead market of the Iberian electricity market (MIBEL) taking into account the generation capacities for 2030. The capacities were identified using the open-access optimization tool Backbone [23] based on 2030 Energy and Climate Plans for Portugal and Spain. The OptiRES.Lines tool is used to obtain the hourly DLR values of the cross-border tie-lines connecting Portugal and Spain, which are compared with a scenario using the SLR used by the TSOs [13]. The open-access coupled version¹ of Multi-Agent Simulators of Competitive Electricity Markets (MASCEM) [24] and Trading of Renewable Production (RESTRade) [25], both being enhanced in the TradeRES project², are used to compute the outputs of the day-ahead and balancing markets, respectively. MASCEM simulates electricity markets with focus on strategic bidding [24]. Over the years, several improvements have been done, namely regarding power flow analysis [26] and interoperability through ontologies [27]. RESTRade simulates the secondary capacity and energy markets, the tertiary energy market and the imbalance settlement [25].

The remainder of the paper is structured as follows. Section II presents the methodology and section III presents the case study. Some concluding remarks are presented in Section IV.

¹This coupled version is available at <https://github.com/TradeRES/hands-on-mascecm-restrade> and their user guides are available at <https://traderes.eu/user-guides/>

II. METHODOLOGY

The power system benefits from using DLR for a more efficient long-run (several years) internal grid expansion planning, such as long-run planning of the tie-lines cross-border capacity. A conservative forecast methodology to compute the meteorological data is needed to feed the DLR methodology, being important to compute the day-ahead tie-lines capacity, avoiding market splitting and a conservative management of local congestions in the short-run.

To plan the grid expansion of future power systems with nearly 100% RES penetrations is also important to plan the generation capacity expansion and forecast the consumption and vRES behaviours in them.

Figure 1 presents the employed methodology.

Figure 1: Methodology to analyse the impact of DLR in electricity markets.

The generation capacity of each country/market zone is optimized using Backbone, which receives limits of each technology capacity and estimates of the consumption and expected variable and fixed costs of the technologies. The goal of Backbone consists in reducing the power system total costs for a given period, including investment, operational and maintenance costs [23].

The OptiRES.Lines tool used to obtain the DLR of overhead conductors is presented in the next section.

A. DLR Analysis: Thermodynamic model of conductors

The thermal inertia of the overhead conductor considering its thermal behaviour computed as the balance of gained and lost heat due to the weather conditions around it and its electrical load, ignoring its radial and axial temperature distribution, is described by the following equation [9].

$$m \cdot C_p \cdot \frac{dT}{dt} = -P_c - P_r + P_s + P_j \quad (1)$$

Where m is the cable mass (Kg/m), C_p is heat capacity of the cable (J/KgK), T is the temperature and t is the time. P_c is the convective cooling, P_r is the radiative cooling, P_s is the solar heating and P_j is the joule heating (all in W/m). To compute these thermal powers shall be used the thermal characteristics of the cables and forecasts of the wind speed and direction, the solar irradiation and the air ambient temperature. The meteorological parameters can be obtained from a NWP model [12]. When it is considered the equilibrium situation the

² <https://traderes.eu/>

body does not have internal energy and the previous equation is simplified to [7],[9]:

$$-P_c - P_r + P_s + P_j = 0 \quad (2)$$

The IEEE 738-2023 [7] and Kuipers & Brown [8] methodologies were modelled as presented in the literature. The CIGRÉ 601 methodology has a problem in its mathematical continuity when passing from natural to forced convection [28], as indicated by Bertinat [9]. During some periods it is possible to obtain negative values of the convective power, to avoid that, in those cases it is considered the internal energy of the cable, using equation (1).

B. Day-ahead and balancing markets

The simulations of the day-ahead and balancing markets are performed using MASCEM and REStTrade, respectively. MASCEM clears the marginal day-ahead market based on a symmetrical auction-based algorithm. It maximizes the social welfare of the participants, similarly to EUPHEMIA, the algorithm used in the European Single Day-ahead Coupling market [16], [24]-[27].

The DAM simulation begins with the definition of simulation settings, where the start and end periods for simulations are specified. Based on these settings, historical data is collected to define new bids. These bids are also generated using data provided by Backbone. After defining the bids, the DAM simulation is executed based on the symmetric pool model, from which the clearing price and quantity of energy transacted are obtained. When clearing the DAM and considering the energy transacted and retrieving the location of each accepted bid, the power flow can be executed to validate the DAM results. This process allows obtaining the power flow (quantity and direction) between two countries within the simulation area. Based on data provided by system operators, if the hourly optimal energy flow between coupled markets/market zones is higher than their commercial cross-border capacity, the markets are separated and they trade only the energy that does not surpass that capacity. The clearing of the day-ahead market impacts balancing markets. All technologies assigned to participate in balancing markets with a day-ahead programmed dispatch have to adapt their participation.

REStTrade included the Portuguese and ENTSO-E models of the asymmetrical and symmetrical procurements of secondary capacity, respectively. It considers the marginal asymmetrical clearing of the secondary and tertiary energy markets. Furthermore, it has the Portuguese and Spanish models of the imbalance settlement [25].

III. CASE STUDY

This case study is devoted to assess the impact of using DLR (using the CIGRÉ 601 methodology [9]) in the occurrence of market splitting in the day-ahead market of the Iberian electricity market (MIBEL). Considering the methodology illustrated in Figure 1, the first step consists in the computation of the optimal generation capacities of Portugal and Spain in

2030. The data and results are analysed from the point of view of Portugal.

A. Optimal generation capacity in Portugal and Spain

The generation capacity of each country was optimized using the Backbone model, considering the National Energy and Climate Plans, forecasts of the expected variable and fixed costs of the technologies and consumption in 2030. The Backbone's input data for the 2030 simulations is available in [29]. The simulation has been performed at an European level, being the Portuguese and Spanish generation capacities presented in Figure 2.

Figure 2: Installed capacity (MW) by technology in Portugal (outside scale) and Spain (inner scale) in 2030.

Using Backbone and considering marginal production prices, it is possible to obtain the optimal dispatch of each technology and an estimation of the wholesale electricity costs and cross-border flows. These values only consider the optimal dispatch without forecast errors or strategic behaviour of the different market players. Using SLR it was predicted 229 market splitting occurrences and a yearly penetration of 87% renewable generation in the Iberian Peninsula.

B. DLR Analysis

In this section, the comparison of the cross-border capacity using DLR with SLR is presented. Tie-lines are spread over the countries (check [17] for their location), but considering that some have two parallel lines, Table I presents their main characteristics.

TABLE I: TIE-LINES CHARACTERISTICS.

Tie-line name and (voltage) level (kV)	Cable type PT/ES	Maximum cable temp. PT/ES [°C]	Amb. temp. variation [°C]
Lindoso-Cartelle 1-2 (400)	Rail	85	15-29
Lagoaça-Aldeadavila (400)	Rail	85	15-32
Pocinho-Aldeadavila 1-2 (220)	Zebra/Lapwing	85	15-32
Pocinho-Saucelle (220)	Zebra	85	15-32
Falagueira-Cedillo (400)	Zambeze	85/70	15-33
Alqueva-Brovaes (400)	Rail	85	15-35
Tavira-Guzmán (400)	Rail	85	15-32

Both TSOs use SLRs considering an incident wind speed of 0.6 m/s and an irradiance of 1000 W/m². The main difference is that the Portuguese TSO considers different monthly ambient (amb.) temperatures (temp.) and the Spanish TSO considers seasonal values.

Figure 3 presents the physical and commercial cross-border capacities and their trading slack (i.e., the difference between the physical and commercial capacities because of technical constraints) considering the thermodynamic characteristics of the cables.

Figure 3: Physical and commercial capacities and their trading slack in Portugal and Spain.

Analysing Figure 3 it is possible to verify a significant slack difference between the physical and commercial capacities. It has been considered that the DLR is applied considering the slack. In this study the DLR methodology uses the data from the tie-lines vertex towers split in-between line section into sectors of 3 kilometres, consistent with the spatial resolution of the meteorological data. When the sector's length is below the 3 kilometres resolution its length is used instead. For each sector, the wind speed and direction, ambient temperature, and solar irradiance are obtained using a NWP model [12]. The data are extracted for the mid-distance point of each line's sector.

Simulating the CIGRÉ 601 methodology with the OptiRES.Lines tool and reducing the import and export capacity slacks to its DLR outputs, it is possible to obtain the import and export day-ahead cross-border capacities presented in Figure 4. Thus, after obtaining the DLR values, the final cross-border capacities are adjusted being limited to the day-ahead commercial import/export capacity hourly values according to the internal grid constraints of both countries. It is a conservative approach in the transition to a more dynamic, capable and weather dependent power system.

Figure 4: SLR and DLR cross-border capacities.

Analysing Figure 4 it is possible to conclude that SLR underestimates the cross-border capacities almost during the

whole year even considering limited DLR values. However, it also overestimates the export and import capacity during 3% and 2.7% of the year (mainly during summer), respectively.

C. Day-ahead and balancing markets outcomes

This section tests the agent-based behaviour of consumers and producers in the day-ahead and balancing markets with the goal of verifying the benefits of considering DLR in the cross-border capacities using MASCEM and RESTRade, respectively.

It is considered that producers bid based on their marginal costs. This study aims at verifying the impact of using different line ratings in the occurrence of market splitting in the DAM and in the costs of electricity in the following two scenarios:

- SLR (Baseline): actual SLR values used by TSOs;
- DLR: both countries limit the DLR outputs considering their import and export capacity slack.

Figure 5 presents the separation cases of the two Iberian markets and their impact on the price difference between the Portuguese and the Spanish markets in the case of market splitting events in the predefined scenarios

Figure 5: Price difference between the Portuguese and Spanish markets.

Analysing Figure 5 it is possible to conclude that Portugal never exports energy to Spain because the price difference is always higher or equal to 0 €/MWh. The simulation of the DAM using SLR and DLR leads to a number of market splitting events of 1512 and 514, respectively. So, by using DLR, the occurrences of market splitting decreased by almost 67%, increasing the price harmonization between Portugal and Spain by decreasing the price difference of their markets from 19 to 12 €/MWh.

Because of the high penetration of vRES, prices are equal to zero in 1356 and 1355 hours in Portugal (PT) and Spain (ES), respectively. In these situations, during around 60% of the time, prices are similar using SLR. This value increases to 80% when DLR is used. Indeed, even considering market splitting events, prices are equal in 520 and 130 of them using SLR and DLR, respectively. This result is mainly explained by the similar generation portfolios in both countries, the simple strategic bidding behaviour of producers based on marginal prices and the high incidence of prices equal to zero.

Figure 6 presents the trading costs in each market zone considering the SLR and DLR capacities.

Figure 6: Liquidity of the DAM per market zone: Portugal (PT), MIBEL (MI) and Spain (ES).

Analysing Figure 6 it is possible to conclude that by considering DLR, the transaction costs in the separated markets reduced by 73%. However, the reduction in the DAM costs is only 1%. The results are not so different in the DLR scenario because while in Portugal prices decrease from 34.93 to 33.66 €/MWh in Spain they increase from 23.56 to 23.90 €/MWh, on average. Figure 7 presents the balancing costs in each scenario.

Figure 7: Balancing costs of the SLR and DLR scenarios in Spain (ES) and Portugal (PT).

From Figure 7 it is possible to conclude that the cross-border capacity does not affect the allocated secondary capacity costs, once the procurement of TSOs is not affected by it. However, it affected the energy balancing costs for both secondary and tertiary energy control by freeing up more competitive power plants from the DAM in the DLR scenario, these costs reduced around 1% in both countries.

Concluding, while using DLR reduced the occurrences of market splitting to almost one third, the wholesale electricity costs only reduced by a bit more than 1% due to the high incidence of low DAM prices.

IV. FINAL REMARKS

Most TSOs use a “steady state” Seasonal Line Rating (SLR) approach to represent transmission line capacity considering very conservative seasonal weather conditions and underestimating the lines’ capacity. This results in an inefficient use of the grid assets, namely, use of oversized cables, increasing the costs of the transmission grid unnecessary. The presented methodology uses a thermodynamic model

considering the experimental presented in the CIGRÉ 601 brochure. The use of dynamic line rating (DLR) can avoid the construction of new transmission lines in the long-run. In the short-run it can avoid congestions, market splitting and the curtailment of renewable generation, but also the degradation of lines and an insecure operation when SLR overestimates the lines’ capacity.

This work presented a methodology to detect the impact of using DLR in future power systems with high penetrations of variable renewable generation. It has been applied in the simulation of the optimal power systems of Portugal and Spain by 2030 using the Backbone model. OptiRES.lines has been used to compute the day-ahead DLR of the cross-border lines connecting these countries. MASCEM has been used to clear the Iberian day-ahead market (DAM) considering the used line ratings. Then, RESTrade has been used to verify the impact of the day-ahead dispatch programs in the real-time balancing prices.

In line with previous works, this study identified an average increase of 30% on the transmission capacity by using DLR, when compared with the use of SLR approach. Around 3% of the time the DLR of the lines is lower than the limits defined by the TSO, which can lead to the saturation of the lines such as to their degradation, and in the worst scenario to their damage.

Results from this study allow to conclude that by considering DLR cross-border capacities the number of market splitting events in the DAM reduced from 1512 to 514, increasing its price harmonization. This reduction represents a decrease in the price difference from 19 (SLR approach) to 12 (DLR approach) €/MWh in those events. This reduction led to a decrease in the wholesale price of electricity above 1%. The adoption of DLR can play a crucial role in meeting the renewable targets set for 2030. It can avoid the construction of new transmission lines in the long-run, while, in short-run, DLR can prevent grid congestion occurrences, market splitting and the curtailment of renewable generation.

ACKNOWLEDGMENT

This work has received funding from the EU Horizon 2020 research and innovation program under project TradeRES (grant agreement No 864276).

REFERENCES

- [1] S. Karimi, P. Musilek, and A. M. Knight, “Dynamic thermal rating of transmission lines: A review”, *Renew. Sustain. Energy Rev.*, vol. 91, April, pp. 600–612, 2018.
- [2] R. Mínguez, R. Martínez, M. Manana, A. Arroyo, R. Domingo, e A. Laso, “Dynamic management in overhead lines: A successful case of reducing restrictions in renewable energy sources integration”, *Electr. Power Syst. Res.*, vol. 173, pp. 135–142, 2019.
- [3] B. P. Bhattarai *et al.*, “Improvement of Transmission Line Ampacity Utilization by Weather-Based Dynamic Line Rating”, *IEEE Trans. Power Deliv.*, vol. 33, n. 4, pp. 1853–1863, 2018.
- [4] A. Arroyo *et al.*, “Comparison between IEEE and CIGRE Thermal Behaviour Standards and Measured Temperature on a 132-kV Overhead Power Line”, *Energies*, vol. 8, n. 12, pp. 13660–13671, Dez. 2015.
- [5] E. Fernandez, I. Albizu, M. T. Bediaauneta, A. J. Mazon, e P. T. Leite, “Review of dynamic line rating systems for wind power integration”, *Renew. Sustain. Energy Rev.*, vol. 53, n. 2016, pp. 80–92, Jan. 2016.

- [6] R. Dupin, A. Michiorri, e G. Kariniotakis, "Optimal Dynamic Line Rating Forecasts Selection Based on Ampacity Probabilistic Forecasting and Network Operators' Risk Aversion", *IEEE Trans. Power Syst.*, vol. 34, n. 4, pp. 2836–2848, 2019.
- [7] IEEE Std. 738-2023, "IEEE Standard for Calculating the Current-Temperature Relationship of Bare Overhead Conductors IEEE Standard for Calculating the Current-Temperature Relationship of Bare Overhead Conductors", 2023. [Online]. Available: <https://doi.org/10.1109/IEEESTD.2023.10382442>
- [8] Ministry of Economy/Portuguese Republic, Portaria no 596/2010, Diário da República, 147, 2010. [Online]. Available: <https://files.diariodarepublica.pt/1s/2010/07/14700/0292302954.pdf?lang=EN>
- [9] J. Iglesias *et al.*, "Guide for thermal rating calculations of overhead lines", CIGRÉ WG B2.43, p. 93, December 2014.
- [10] A. W. Abboud *et al.*, "Using Computational Fluid Dynamics of Wind Simulations Coupled with Weather Data to Calculate Dynamic Line Ratings", *IEEE Trans. Power Deliv.*, vol. PP, p. 1, 2019.
- [11] F. Teng, R. Dupin, A. Michiorri, G. Kariniotakis, Y. Chen, e G. Strbac, "Understanding the Benefits of Dynamic Line Rating Under Multiple Sources of Uncertainty", *IEEE Trans. Power Syst.*, vol. 33, n. 3, pp. 3306–3314, 2018.
- [12] A. Couto *et al.*, "Impact of the dynamic line rating analysis in regions with high levels of wind and solar PV generation", in 2020 IEEE PES Innovative Smart Grid Technologies Europe (ISGT-Europe), pp. 1206-1210, IEEE, 26 Oct. 2020.
- [13] A. Michiorri *et al.*, "Forecasting for dynamic line rating", *Renew. Sustain. Energy Rev.*, vol. 52, pp. 1713–1730, 2015.
- [14] Y. Li, Y. Wang, e Q. Chen, "Study on the impacts of meteorological factors on distributed photovoltaic accommodation considering dynamic line parameters", *Appl. Energy*, vol. 259, n. October 2019, p. 114133, 2020.
- [15] A. W. Abboud *et al.*, "Coupling computational fluid dynamics with the high resolution rapid refresh model for forecasting dynamic line ratings", *Electr. Power Syst. Res.*, vol. 170, n. February, pp. 326–337, 2019.
- [16] Á. Slesiz, P. Sörös and D. Raisz, "Algorithmic properties of the all-European day-ahead electricity market", in International Conference on the European Energy Market, IEEE, pp. 1–6 28 May 2004.
- [17] H. Algarvio *et al.*, "Increase cross-border capacity to reduce market splitting of day-ahead electricity markets-A dynamic line rating approach", in IEEE/PES Transmission and Distribution Conference and Exposition (T&D) (pp. 1-5). IEEE, 2022.
- [18] T. Haring, D. Kirschen, and G. Andersson, "Incentive compatible imbalance settlement", *IEEE Transactions on Power Systems*, vol. 30(6), pp. 33383346, 2015.
- [19] R. Lacal Arantegui e A. Jäger-Waldau, «Photovoltaics and wind status in the European Union after the Paris Agreement», *Renew. Sustain. Energy Rev.*, vol. 81, Part 2, pp. 2460–2471, Jan. 2018.
- [20] H. Algarvio, F. Lopes, A. Couto, J. Santana and A. Estanqueiro, "Effects of Regulating the European Internal Market on the integration of Variable Renewable Energy", *WIREs: Energy Environ.*, vol. 8(6),e346, 2019.
- [21] H. Algarvio, J. Duque and A. Couto, "D3.1 - Development of DLR analysis and power system models", OptiGrid report, July 2021.
- [22] X. Zhang, Z. Ying, Y. Chen and X. Chen, "A thermal model for calculating axial temperature distribution of overhead conductor under laboratory conditions", *Electr. Power Syst. Res.*, vol. 166, pp. 223-31, 2019.
- [23] N. Helistö *et al.*, "Backbone—An adaptable energy systems modelling framework", *Energies*, vol. 12(17), p. 3388, 2019.
- [24] Z. Vale, T. Pinto, I. Praca, and H. Morais, "MASCEM: Electricity Markets Simulation with Strategic Agents", *Intell. Syst. IEEE*, vol. 26, n.o 2, pp. 9–17, 2011.
- [25] H. Algarvio, F. Lopes, A. Couto and A. Estanqueiro, "Participation of wind power producers in day-ahead and balancing markets: An overview and a simulation-based study", *WIREs: Energy Environ.*, vol. 8(5),e343, 2019.
- [26] B. Veiga, G. Santos, T. Pinto, R. Faia, C. Ramos, and Z. Vale, "Simulation tools for electricity markets considering power flow analysis", *Energy*, vol. 275, p. 127494, 2023.
- [27] G. Santos, H. Morais, T. Pinto, J. M. Corchado, and Z. Vale, "Intelligent energy systems ontology to support markets and power systems co-simulation interoperability", *Energy Convers. Manag.* X, vol. 20, p. 100495, 2023..
- [28] M. Maksić *et al.*, "Cooling of overhead power lines due to the natural convection", *International Journal of Electrical Power & Energy Systems*, vol. 113, pp. :333-43.
- [29] N. Helistö *et al.*, "TradeRES scenario database". [Online]. Available: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10829706>